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CONTENTS

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES.....	51
Mamadiev Elyor	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY GUEST HOUSES	55
Boynazarov Ulugbek Egamberdievich	
IMPROVING METHODS OF ORGANIZING AND DEVELOPING DOMESTIC TOURISM MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN	61
Daminov Mirvokhid Isroilovich	
THE IMPACT AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR.....	67
Dilsora Ibodovna Ibodova	
IMPACT OF STUDENTS AGED OVER 40 ON ECONOMIC ACTIVITY AND BUDGETING BASED ON THE COMPETENCY ECOSYSTEM	74
Nigora Ikrom qizi Primova	
ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ: ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ И СЦЕНАРНОЕ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ НА 2026–2030 ГОДЫ	80
Юсуфов Шерзодбек Бахтиёр угли	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE PROCUREMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL ENTERPRISES	87
Ergashev Jahongir Bakhodirovich	
MULTIVARIATE ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING HOUSEHOLD INCOME IN SURXONDARYO REGION	93
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor qizi	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЦИФРОВЫХ УСЛУГ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА	99
Юсифов Магамед Исмаил оглу, Гасанли Расул Шахин оглу, Белалова Гузаль Анваровна	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY.....	105
Xudayberdiyeva Kamila Sadiilloyevna, Fozilova Zumrad Ahmadovna	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	111
Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi	
КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО АГРОПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО ИНТЕГРИРОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ МОДЕЛИ АНР-TOPSIS	115
Аликулов А.Б.	
APPLICATION OF CLUSTER METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE AND IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS IN SAMARKAND CITY	121
Tashov Mizrob Maxmudovich	
THE ROLE AND PROSPECTS OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE SERVICE SECTOR.....	130
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL ENTERPRISES	135
Nigora Zokirjon qizi Toxirova	
CURRENT STATE OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE METHODOLOGY OF ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY INDICATORS	142
Temurbek Olimovich Mamayunusov	
PRESUPPOSITION SHIFTS IN CROSS-LINGUISTIC RENDERING OF ANECDOTAL NARRATIVES:	

A COMPARATIVE INQUIRY INTO TRIGGER RETENTION AND TRANSFORMATION	148
Umaraliyeva Dildora Taxirjanovna	
DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND RURAL PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY: AN EMPIRICAL ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS	156
Bek Hunsia, Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova	
COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF WOMEN'S LABOR ACTIVITY ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE ECONOMIC SYSTEM	164
Ahrorova Asila Abduaziz qizi	
IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL ENVIRONMENT	170
Azizbek Khurramov	
FORMATION OF FINANCIAL RESULTS AT MOTOR TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES	180
Shanazarova Nilufar Baratovna	
ARIMA-BASED ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF SURKHANDARYA REGION	185
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
ASSESSMENT OF AGRARIAN SECTOR EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE SFA MODEL	192
Utanov Bunyod Kuvandikovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ ВНЕШНИМ ДОЛГОМ	196
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович, Жуманазаров Шахобиддин Дилмурод угли	
MODERN METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO MANAGING EDUCATIONAL SERVICES MARKETING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	201
Shamshieva Nargizakhon Nosirkhuja kizi	
FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN AND DOMESTIC COTTON GINNING ENTERPRISES: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, DIAGNOSTICS, AND IMPROVEMENT DIRECTIONS	208
Orif Jumayevich Murodov	
ANALYSIS OF THE INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF STATE INTERVENTION IN THE PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN	219
Atakulov Askad Raimkulovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ФОРМАЛИЗАЦИИ НЕФОРМАЛЬНОЙ ЗАНЯТОСТИ И РАСШИРЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ В АГРАРНЫХ РЕГИОНАХ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ)	224
Бобоназарова Юлдуз Ботировна	
THE ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY AND ITS ROLE IN INDUSTRIAL ECONOMICS	229
Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna, Aipova Iroda Ikramovna	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM DEVELOPING COUNTRIES	234
Ismatova Diyora Sirojiddin qizi, Ubaydullayeva Gulchexra Erkabayevna	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ И РЕСУРСНАЯ АДАПТИВНОСТЬ ОТРАСЛИ МАШИНОСТРОЕНИЯ В РОССИИ, КИТАЕ, ИНДИИ	239
Викторова Наталья Геннадьевна, Абрамчикова Наталья Викторовна, Ван Байянь	
ENSURING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT	249
Aminova Naima Umar qizi	
STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH: PRACTICAL APPROACHES AND IMPROVEMENTS	253
Baymuradov Shokhruxh Makhmudovich, Dilmurodov Komiljon Ahmad o'g'li	
IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SMALL ENTERPRISES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR (A CASE STUDY OF TASHKENT REGION)	259

Ashirov Alisher	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN	264
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	
INNOVATIVE IDEAS OF YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS AND INFRASTRUCTURE FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INNOVATIVE BUSINESSES	270
Ergashev Oybek Khaydaralievich	
MARKETING CHARACTERISTICS OF POSITIONING ORGANIC DRIED FRUIT PRODUCTS IN INTERNATIONAL MARKETS	274
Khidirov Shokhrukh	
TYOLOGIZATION OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL AND DEVELOPMENT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DISTRICTS OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON STATISTICAL AND NEURAL NETWORK APPROACHES.....	280
Normurodov Asliddin Alijon ugli	
THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN ANALYSING THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE AUDIT OF FINANCIAL LIABILITIES	291
Palvanov Xusniddin Bekimmatovich	
DIGITAL SKILLS AND LABOUR PRODUCTIVITY: A SCENARIO ANALYSIS BASED ON AN INTEGRATED STATISTICAL MODEL	297
Madraimov Xabibulla Madaminovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СТРУКТУРЫ АКТИВОВ И ПАССИВОВ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	303
Т.И. Бобакулов	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ ВНЕШНЕТОРГОВУЮ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ КОМПАНИЙ С ДОКУМЕНТАРНЫМИ АККРЕДИТИВАМИ.....	308
М.Т. Ибодуллаева	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОСНОВНЫМИ СРЕДСТВАМИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	312
Мусаева Жамила Кароматовна	
ПРОБЛЕМНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	320
Ш.Т. Ибодуллаев	
THE IMPORTANCE OF STATE SUPPORT AND INVESTMENT POLICY IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF MASS MEDIA ENTERPRISES.....	325
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
CURRENT STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF MOTOR TRANSPORT SERVICES	329
Rakhimov Azamat Hamrakulovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЭКСТРЕМАЛЬНЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ В ОЦЕНКЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ.....	333
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
MULTI-FACTOR ECONOMETRIC MODELS OF WATER RESOURCE USE IN ENSURING REGIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY.....	341
Xaitbaev Jasurbek Otaxanovich	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРАКТИКИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ДОКУМЕНТООБОРОТА В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ.....	345
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович	
THE WAYS OF IMPROVING COMPETITIVENESS IN COMPANIES OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	350
Buriev Khakim Toshimovich, Usmanov Ilxom Achilovich, Tolibov Abduazim Zoxid ugli	
MACROECONOMIC MODELS AND PROSPECTS OF TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	357
Sharipboyev Hasanboy Marks ugli, Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
THE IMPACT OF HRM PRACTICES ON ACADEMIC STAFF WORK EFFICIENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	366
Sultonboyeva Munira Bahodirovna, Sultanova Kamila Muktorali Kizi	

THE ECONOMIC ROLE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	374
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi	
ОЦЕНКА ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КРУПНОГО РОГАТОГО СКОТА, ЗАВЕЗЁННОГО В РЕСПУБЛИКУ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН ИЗ-ЗА РУБЕЖА, С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ	378
Аскарова Нилуфар Бахтияровна	
COOPERATIVE MECHANISMS FOR REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A FRAMEWORK ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL TOURISM ENTERPRISE PARTNERSHIPS.....	382
Shohruzbek Ruziyev	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISES: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND MODERN DEVELOPMENT TRENDS	393
Matkuliev Akbar Karimovich	
TAX INCENTIVES GRANTED TO ENTERPRISES LOCATED IN SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES	397
Torayeva Nafisa Odiljonovna	
REQUIREMENTS FOR TRANSITIONING TO ELECTRONIC BUSINESS AND CONDITIONS FOR DIGITALIZATION.....	402
Ismoilov Diyorbek Ismoiljon ugli	
DEVELOPMENT OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN ENSURING A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY AND ENERGY SECURITY	407
Ergash Bobobekov	
ANALYSIS OF WAGE DYNAMICS IN THE EXAMPLE OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON PANEL DATA.....	412
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor kizi	
THE ROLE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN IMPROVING THE MARKET COMPETITIVENESS OF CARPET INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	420
Arzieva Sevinch Shomurot kizi	
CONSUMER PROPERTIES OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN: TRADITIONS, TRANSFORMATION AND NEW QUALITY STANDARDS.....	425
Gayrat Pardaev	
DIRECTIONS FOR STIMULATING ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE TAX SYSTEM.....	431
Yakhshimuratova Khasiyat Khudaybergenovna	
THE ROLE OF E-COMMERCE IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS	435
Kambaraliyeva Intizor Suxrobovna	
Aliyarov Olim Abdug‘aparovich	
ISSUES OF IMPROVING PRE-TRIAL TAX DISPUTE RESOLUTION MECHANISMS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	439
Solihova Xumora Xasan kizi	
INCREASING THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF DIVIDEND POLICY IN UZBEKISTAN COMPANIES.....	446
Akmal Komiljonovich Shermukhamedov	
COMMUNITY-BASED HERITAGE TOURISM MODELS AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING HANDICRAFT DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	451
Olimjonova Farog‘at Dilmurod qizi	
Amiriddinova Muslima Zayniddin qizi	
ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПЕРЕХОДНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ОПЫТ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	458
Шоахмедов Шоҳрух Шорахимович	

OF EFFECTIVE USE OF AGRICULTURAL LAND	464
Umarov Muzaffar Yusupbayevich	
ECONOMIC CONTENT OF INTANGIBLE ASSETS IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AND SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THEIR RECOGNITION	469
Ishankulov Izzatilla Nurillaevich	
DETERMINANTS OF NON-PERFORMING LOANS IN SERVICE SECTOR LENDING AND CREDIT RISK MITIGATION MECHANISMS	473
Nurmukhammedov Abdijabbar Yunusovich	
ESG INTEGRATION PRACTICES INTO CORPORATE CULTURE SYSTEM IN THE JOINTSTOCK SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN: A CASE STUDY OF “DORI-DARMON” JSC.....	479
Sadikova Muslima Alisher kizi	
DEVELOPMENT OF THE METAL MARKET IN THE TASHKENT REGION AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT	485
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
SMALL BUSINESS AS A CATALYST FOR REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS WITH EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	491
Jo‘rayev Ilhomjon Kamolidinovich	
ISSUES OF DEVELOPING DEPOSIT OPERATIONS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	497
Rahimov Akmal Matyaqubovich	
IMPROVING TEXTILE LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	503
Isroilov Madaminjon Mukhsinovich	
FEATURES OF SUMMARIZING AND EVALUATING THE RESULTS OF FINANCIAL STATEMENT AUDITING IN UZBEKISTAN PRACTICE	509
Isroil Ismoilovich Meliev	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ФИНАНСАМИ И СОЦИАЛЬНОЕ РАВЕНСТВО В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ МЕТОДОЛОГИИ РЕФА С ДИСТРИБУТИВНЫМ АНАЛИЗОМ НА ОСНОВЕ ПОДХОДА SEQ.....	516
Зокиржонов Мухаммадсодик Равшанбек угли	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY: CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	530
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF COST ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS IN AQUACULTURE CLUSTERS: IFRS INTEGRATION, ECONOMETRIC MODELING, AND ESG PERSPECTIVES.....	537
Shodiev Aslam Rahmatilloevich	
APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS FOR PREDICTING CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS	544
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas	
SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION UNDER WATER SCARCITY: GLOBAL EXPERIENCE AND PROSPECTS FOR UZBEKISTAN	550
Sodiqova Nigora Turayevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF BUSINESS ENTITIES IN THE BUKHARA REGION	555
Djurayeva Munira Sadillovna	
EVALUATION OF THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORTS IN THE BUKHARA REGION	560
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	

ADVANCING AN INTEGRATED STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY FOR COMMERCIAL BANKS' DIGITAL ACTIVITIES AND CREDIT PORTFOLIO QUALITY	565
Rakhmataliev Muzaffar Eshdavlatovich	
EFFECTIVENESS OF USING BIOLOGICAL METHODS IN PLANT PROTECTION: STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF DISTRIBUTION STRATEGY AND PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION DENSITY	570
Suyundikova Dilafroz Mamarajabovna	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЯ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ «КАРТЫ ПРОЗРАЧНОСТИ ПО МСФО» НА ОСНОВЕ КЛАСТЕРИЗАЦИИ АКЦИОНЕРНЫХ ОБЩЕСТВ ПО УРОВНЮ КАЧЕСТВА.....	577
Лутфуллаев Сардорбек Уткур угли	
INDICATOR-BASED IMPROVED METHODOLOGY FOR DETERMINING INTERNAL AUDIT SIGNIFICANCE LIMITS IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR.....	586
Ismatillayev Baypolat Khushvaqtovich	
METHODOLOGY FOR IDENTIFYING CASHGENERATING UNITS AND ADJUSTING THE DISCOUNT RATE TO NATIONAL CAPITAL MARKET CONDITIONS IN THE IMPAIRMENT ASSESSMENT OF LONG-TERM ASSETS	593
Fayzullayev Begzod Bakhtiyor o'g'li	
IMPROVING THE SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO THE FUNCTIONAL CLASSIFICATION OF INVENTORIES IN COMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES	599
Jamilov Jushkin Jonon o'g'li	
IMPROVING THE CHART OF ACCOUNTS AND ANALYTICAL ACCOUNTING FOR FINANCIAL INVESTMENTS IN ACCORDANCE WITH IFRS 9.....	604
Jumamurodov Toliboy Yeldashbayevich	

IMPROVING THE CHART OF ACCOUNTS AND ANALYTICAL ACCOUNTING FOR FINANCIAL INVESTMENTS IN ACCORDANCE WITH IFRS 9

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Abstract. The article examines the improvement of the national Chart of Accounts and analytical accounting for the recognition of financial investments in accordance with IFRS 9 “Financial Instruments”. It is substantiated that the current Chart of Accounts lacks sub-accounts that enable financial investments to be accounted for by measurement method. As a result of the research, a procedure is developed for opening nine additional sub-accounts to accounts 0610 “Long-term Financial Investments” and 5810 “Current Financial Investments”, as well as for maintaining their synthetic and analytical accounting. The proposed procedure ensures data transparency and contributes to bringing financial statements into compliance with international standards.

Keywords: financial investments, IFRS 9, Chart of Accounts, sub-account, synthetic accounting, analytical accounting, accounting entries, amortized cost, fair value, ECL.

Аннотация. В статье исследуются вопросы совершенствования национального Плана счетов бухгалтерского учёта и аналитического учёта финансовых инвестиций в соответствии с требованиями МСФО (IFRS) 9 «Финансовые инструменты». Обосновано, что действующий План счетов не содержит субсчетов, позволяющих вести учёт финансовых инвестиций в разрезе методов их последующей оценки. По результатам исследования разработан порядок открытия девяти дополнительных субсчетов к счетам 0610 «Долгосрочные финансовые инвестиции» и 5810 «Краткосрочные финансовые инвестиции», а также предложена методика организации их синтетического и аналитического учёта. Применение предложенного подхода обеспечивает повышение прозрачности учётной информации и способствует приведению финансовой отчётности в соответствие с требованиями международных стандартов финансовой отчётности.

Ключевые слова: финансовые инвестиции, МСФО (IFRS) 9, План счетов бухгалтерского учёта, субсчёт, синтетический учёт, аналитический учёт, бухгалтерские проводки, амортизированная стоимость, справедливая стоимость, ожидаемые кредитные убытки (ECL).

INTRODUCTION

The transition to the preparation of financial statements based on International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) has become one of the priority areas of accounting reform in Uzbekistan. In accordance with the relevant resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, large enterprises and joint-stock companies are preparing financial statements in accordance with IFRS. Under these conditions, the recognition, measurement, and accounting of financial investments based on the requirements of IFRS 9 “Financial Instruments” have become an urgent practical task.

The need to account for financial investments by measurement method is primarily explained by the requirements for the reliability and comparability of financial reporting. According to IFRS 9, the same financial asset may be measured differently depending on the applicable business model. Therefore, when accounting for such assets, it is important to establish a system of sub-accounts that clearly reflects the measurement method. In the absence of such a system, information on financial investments is recorded in a generalized form, while their regrouping for reporting purposes creates additional workload and increases the risk of errors.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research employed methods of analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, grouping, logical generalization, balance summarization, and the double-entry method of accounting.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

To account for financial investments in accordance with IFRS 9, they should be classified into three groups according to their measurement method: investments measured at amortized cost, investments measured at fair value through other comprehensive income (FVOCI), and investments measured at fair value through profit or loss (FVTPL).

To implement this classification in accounting practice, it is proposed to open separate sub-accounts for each group, including sub-accounts for impairment allowances, within the existing accounts 0610 “Long-term Financial Investments” and 5810 “Current Financial Investments”.

As a result of the research, a system consisting of nine sub-accounts was developed, allowing financial investments to be accounted for by measurement method and holding period, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Proposed subaccounts for accounting for financial investments under IFRS 9

Invoice	Naming	Evaluation method
0611	Long-term financial investments valued at amortized cost	Depreciation Cost (AC)
0612	Long-term financial investments valued at FVOCI	Fair value (via OCI)
0613	Long-term financial investments measured at FVTPL	Fair value (through profit or loss)
0614	Strategic investments in subsidiaries, affiliates and joint ventures	Cost/participation
0619	Reserve for impairment of long-term financial investments	ECL (counter-asset)
5811	Current financial investments valued at amortized cost	Depreciation Cost (AC)
5812	Current financial investments valued at FVOCI	Fair value (via OCI)
5813	Current financial investments measured at FVTPL	Fair value (through profit or loss)
5819	Provision for impairment of current financial investments	ECL (counter-asset)

This table shows that five sub-accounts (0611–0619) are proposed for long-term financial investments, while four sub-accounts (5811–5819) are proposed for current financial investments. In addition, sub-account 0614 is allocated for long-term investments to account for strategic investments in subsidiaries, associates, and joint ventures, since such investments are usually long-term in nature.

In both account groups, sub-accounts 0619 and 5819 are intended to account for impairment allowances for financial investments as contra-asset accounts.

Based on the proposed system of sub-accounts, standard accounting entries for financial investments can be formed. The table presents the main transactions related to the recognition of financial investments, their subsequent measurement, the accrual of interest income, the creation of impairment allowances, and the derecognition of investments (Table 2).

Table 2
Proposed basic accounting transfers for financial investments¹

Economic practices	Debit	Credit	Explanation
The investment is recognized at amortized cost	0611 (5811)	5110, 5530	Purchase price
Calculated interest income (AC)	4830	9520	Effective interest method
FVOCI investment remeasured at fair value (increase)	0612 (5812)	8530	Difference in Equity (OCI)
FVTPL investment remeasured at fair value (increase)	0613 (5813)	9520	The difference is the financial result
The fair value of the FVTPL investment has decreased.	9620	0613 (5813)	The difference is the financial result
Impairment reserve (ECL) established	9620	0619 (5819)	Expected credit losses
Investment sold (saved)	5110	0611–0613	The carrying amount is written off
A gain on the sale was recognised	5110	9520	Sales value difference

A synthetic account for the proposed sub-accounts is maintained within each group. In this case, the debit balances of sub-accounts 0611, 0612, 0613, 0614 and their current counterparts 5811–5813 represent the carrying amount of financial investments, while the credit balances of sub-accounts 0619 and 5819 represent the impairment allowance.

In the financial statements, the net carrying amount of investments is determined as the difference between the balances of the relevant sub-accounts and the impairment allowance. This ensures the correct presentation of financial investments in the statement of financial position by measurement method.

¹ Author development

Analytical accounting for financial investments should be maintained for each investment object. The following are proposed as the main analytical accounting dimensions: type of investment, such as bonds, shares, deposits, or equity interests; issuer or counterparty; measurement method or group; purchase date and maturity; nominal and carrying amount; interest rate and yield; and impairment stage, including the ECL stage.

Maintaining analytical accounting in these dimensions makes it possible to collect and analyze information on financial investments across various sections (Table 3).

Table 3
Analytical account card of financial investments (recommended details)²

Props	Contents	Importance
Investment type	Bond, share, deposit, share	Classification and grouping in the report
Issuer / counterparty	The name of the investment object	Concentration risk assessment
Subaccount (group)	Between 0611–5819	Determination of the evaluation method
Nominal and balance value	Contractual and account value	Financial reporting article
Interest rate / income	Effective interest and income	Calculation of interest income
ECL stage	Stage 1, 2 or 3	Determining the provision for impairment

The proposed analytical accounting details allow data on financial investments to be systematically collected for both accounting and audit purposes. In particular, data at the ECL stage level is important for the accurate calculation of impairment allowances and for risk assessment during the audit process. Data at the issuer and counterparty level serves to identify the concentration of financial investments and assess credit risk.

It is advisable to use modern information systems and accounting software for analytical accounting. In this case, an electronic card should be maintained for each investment object, in which the above details are automatically recorded and updated. This makes it possible to quickly generate reports on financial investments in various analytical sections, as well as to conduct audit procedures remotely and selectively. Thus, the proposed analytical accounting system also creates a basis for the digitalization of financial investment accounting.

The practical application of the developed procedure was considered using the accounting practices of Uzbektelecom JSC and Uzbekistan Post JSC as examples. It was substantiated that government bonds included in the financial investments of these entities should be recorded in sub-accounts 0611 or 5811, term deposits in sub-account 0611, and strategic equity investments in sub-account 0614. This makes it possible to separately account for financial investments by measurement method and to present them in the financial statements in accordance with the requirements of IFRS 9.

An important advantage of the proposed sub-account system is its direct connection with financial statement items. Each sub-account corresponds to a specific item of the statement of financial position or the statement of profit or loss and other comprehensive income. This prevents subjective grouping when preparing financial statements and ensures consistency of reporting. Table 4 shows the relationship between the proposed sub-accounts and financial statement items (Table 4).

Table 4
Relationship of subaccounts to financial statement items³

Subaccount	Financial reporting fashion	Evaluation and reflection
0611, 5811	Financial assets at amortized cost	In the balance sheet depreciation value
0612, 5812	Financial assets at fair value (OCI)	At fair value on the balance sheet; the difference is in capital
0613, 5813	Financial assets at fair value (result).	At fair value on the balance sheet; the difference is the result
0614	Investments in subsidiaries and affiliates	In the cost or equity method
0619, 5819	Reserve for impairment of financial assets	A substance that reduces the balance sheet value

² Author development

³ Author development

When a financial investment is sold or otherwise disposed of, its carrying amount is credited to the relevant sub-account, while the sale proceeds are debited to cash or accounts receivable. The difference between the sale proceeds and the carrying amount is recognized in profit or loss.

When an investment measured at FVOCI is disposed of, the revaluation difference previously accumulated in equity, as part of other comprehensive income, is accounted for in accordance with the requirements of IFRS 9. For debt instruments, it is reclassified to profit or loss; for equity instruments, it remains within equity. This procedure can be clearly implemented through the proposed system of sub-accounts.

Thus, the proposed system of sub-accounts enables consistent accounting for the entire life cycle of financial investments, from initial recognition to disposal, within the framework of the relevant measurement method. This not only improves the quality of accounting but also increases the reliability and international comparability of financial reporting. The proposed analytical accounting details form the necessary information base for making management decisions on financial investments and conducting audits.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

As a result of the research, the following conclusions and recommendations were formulated.

First, it was substantiated that the current Chart of Accounts does not contain sub-accounts that allow financial investments to be accounted for separately according to the measurement methods required by IFRS 9. This complicates the transparent presentation of investments in financial statements.

Second, it was proposed to open nine additional sub-accounts within accounts 0610 and 5810: 0611, 0612, 0613, 0614, 0619, 5811, 5812, 5813, and 5819. These sub-accounts make it possible to account for financial investments measured at amortized cost, FVOCI, and FVTPL, as well as impairment allowances.

Third, standard accounting entries and a procedure for maintaining synthetic and analytical accounting for the proposed sub-accounts were developed. The main analytical accounting details were identified, including investment type, issuer, measurement group, value, and ECL stage.

Fourth, the implementation of the developed procedure ensures the transparency of information on financial investments, aligns financial reporting with the requirements of IFRS 9, and facilitates risk assessment during the audit process.

The proposed procedure for improving the Chart of Accounts and analytical accounting for financial investments based on IFRS 9 may serve as a practical guide for business entities in developing their accounting policies and preparing financial statements in accordance with international standards.

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